

Statistical analysis of carbon dioxide emission and its effect with population in different countries

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Statistical analysis of carbon dioxide emission and its effect with population in different countries

Abstract—This research addresses the critical global issue of rising carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, a primary driver of global warming and the greenhouse effect. While complex problems often demand sophisticated analytical methods, statistical analysis provides a powerful pathway for distilling insights from vast and complex data sources. This paper employs statistical modeling to investigate and quantify the primary anthropogenic drivers of CO₂ emissions. The analysis focuses on key contributing factors, including population growth, industrial activity (fuel combustion in manufacturing and power generation), and deforestation. By systematically evaluating these variables, the study aims to identify significant correlations and provide a data-driven framework to inform targeted mitigation strategies and policy interventions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Presenting the solution of complex problem in a easiest way people are using a lot of analytical method. However, statistical analysis is one of them. In order to data science path, it has a great impact to generate the easiest solution for a complex problem or for the huge amount of data sources. The world is a huge place where everyday people are making a lot of complex problem. The carbon-die-oxide emission is on of that problem. However, most of the reputed countries are trying to solve it but its result is not that much visible. As a result, the world is getting warmer and warmer day by day. In the meantime, people and other researcher are also working with this critical problem and trying to find a way to solve it. This carbon-die-oxide is making a lot of green house gas effect on our atmosphere. One of the major reason for increasing carbon-die-oxide in our world is the huge amount of population. On the other hand, there is another major issue which is also the reason for the carbon-die-oxide extension is called deforestation. However, there are other resources which is making the carbon-dioxide such as gaseous, liquid, solid fuel. People making industries and manufactured factories as well as electricity and atomic power plant [1].

II. BACKGROUND RESEARCH

The researcher found out that today's world producing a lot of carbon-dioxide and its killing our earth too fast. Therefore, in this category, the researcher took a collection of data from 1960-2020 year for 34 countries which cover 19 major areas carbon- dioxide emission. However, the researcher tried to present the complex problem in a easiest way to the viewer about the carbon-dioxide effects on our earth. This research covers the major analytical part of the CO₂ data such as comprehensive, correlation, regression and comparative analysis. For doing all of this analysis we used the SAS programming

language [2]. Firstly, in comprehensive analysis the researcher indicates the overall summary of the selected dataset using scatter plot and defining the overall mean, median, mode, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis [3]. Secondly, we tried to work with the correlation analysis between the data variables of our dataset. Therefore, we used one variable and other five variable to do the analysis. the five variable are population, CO₂ emission from transport, CO₂ emission from electricity, CO₂ emission from manufacture and the GDP growth of a country. Thirdly, the researcher worked with the regression analysis where the variable are CO₂ emission total and the population total of a country. Here we used the scatter plot and fit plot to analysis our regression. However, CO₂ emission total data is used a regressor and the population total is used as dependent variable in this analysis. we can analyze the intercept from this regression analysis [4]. Finally, the last one is comparative analysis. In this analysis, we used a method called one-way ANOVA testing with our dataset where we mentioned the country name from our dataset as a predictor and the independent variable we used total value column [5].

III. EXPLORATION OF DATA SET

The dataset is basically a collection of data table. It can be a different format such as CSV, excel, text etc. However, for this research we have used a dataset which is the excel file. The excel file contains 19 column and 645 rows into it. As we mentioned earlier, the data has 34 country and 19 objective for each country which is representing as a series name in our dataset. For each series name there is a series code mentioned. If we try to find the specific series of data for every country, we can filter the data using this series code. However, into the dataset there are another column into the last which is basically the total value of all year. This can help us to do the analysis for a specific series. The dataset or table picture is given below so that it can give us a clear idea what we used for our analysis. The most important thing is that the data is cleaned and normalized. Into the dashboard section, the researcher explained already how the data was cleaned and normalized.

The definition is already given above about the dataset. One thing need to add that is we used the time series as a year basis from 1960-2020 with 5 years gap for each interval of year. The variable name we mentioned for our dataset is same as the column name of the file such as country_name, country_code, series_name, series_code, year_1960_imp, year_1965_imp, year_1970_imp, year_1975_imp, year_1980_imp, year_1985_imp, year_1990_imp, year_1995_imp, year_2000_imp,

The screenshot shows an Excel spreadsheet with a grid of data. The columns are labeled with years from 2005 to 2020, and the rows contain numerical values representing CO2 emissions for different series codes.

Fig. 1. Dataset Excel File

year_2005_imp, year_2010_imp, year_2015_imp, year_2020_imp.

IV. OUTLIER DETECTION WITH SAS

Outlier is an observation of data which basically behave different than other values of a dataset. It is normal that every dataset would have outlier. However, if the dataset has a lot of outlier into it then it creates a great problem for analysis. On the other hand, there are less number of outlier present into the dataset. Its not create any problem for analysis. The researcher presented a process for detecting outlier using SAS programming language. Therefore, In this example, the researcher measured 3 types of series data from the dataset to detect outlier of it.

A. Outlier for population

```

1 data total_population;
2 set co2_data.sheet1;
3 where series_code = 'SP.POP.TOTL';
4 population_total = total_value;
5 run;
6 proc sgplot data=total_population;
7 vbox population_total;
8 title "Outlier for population series data";
9 run;

```


Fig. 2. Outlier for population series data

B. Outlier for CO₂ emission

```

1 data co2_emission;
2 set co2_data.sheet1;
3 where series_code = 'EN.ATM.CO2E.KT';
4 co2_emission_total = total_value;
5 run;
6 proc sgplot data=co2_emission;
7 vbox co2_emission_total;
8 title "Outlier for co2 emission series data";
9 run;

```

Fig. 3. Outlier for CO₂ emission series data

C. Outlier for CO₂ emission from transport

```

1 data co2_emission_transport;
2 set co2_data.sheet1;
3 where series_code = 'EN.CO2.TRAN.ZS';
4 co2_transpot_total = total_value;
5 run;
6 proc sgplot data=co2_emission_transport;
7 vbox co2_transpot_total;
8 title "Outlier for co2 emission transport series
9 data";
run;

```

Fig. 4. Outlier for CO₂ emission from transport

V. ANALYSIS

It is important to do the Statistical Analysis for any kind of research. However, for our data task. We are doing our work with Carbon-die-oxide emission for different types of countries. This Analysis section divided into four part. In each part we will see how our data deal with the SAS programming languages and its output. However, we are going to find out comprehensive, correlation, regression and comparative analysis.

A. SAS (Comprehensive Descriptive Statistical Analysis)

The comprehensive analysis of a research task find out the complete statistical analysis of the data. This analysis touch every aspects of the data and give the overall situation of the data. However, we are working with the data so it will give us the decision based on our dataset. Here we are going to use the SAS programming to get the result of this analysis.

1) *Step 1*: we need to make a library of our dataset. Making library of the dataset help us to load data from SAS environment easily. On the other hand, library making help us to migrate our other format dataset to SAS format of dataset. Here below code will do our library making task. Our dataset is basically in excel format. So, it will create our dataset to SAS dataset. There is default syntax in SAS programming language called 'libname' help us to make library into our SAS environment.

```
1 /* making a sas library of our work excel file*/
2 libname co2_data xlsx 'C:\Users\julhas\Desktop\
  sas_work\cleaned_data_co2.xlsx';
```

After running above code, we will see that our library already made into the SAS guide software(Figure 5).

Fig. 5. SAS Software library CO2_DATA added

2) *Step 2*: Now we are ready to go with the comprehensive analysis. From the question requirement we need to find out the mean, median, mode, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis of our dataset. However, in our dataset we have separate year value as well as the total year sum value columns. We will do the comprehensive analysis for total year value. In to our dataset, we have year 1960-2020 data. However, for this data we calculated a final row called total value. If we do the comprehensive analysis for the total year value, we will get the complete statistical analysis for our dataset.

```
1 /* ----- comprehensive descriptive statistical
  analysis (e.g., Mean, Median, Mode, Standard
  deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis)
  ----->*/
```

```
2 data all_data;
3   set co2_data.sheet1;
4 run;
5 proc univariate data=all_data;
6   var total_value;
7   title "comprehensive analysis using total value
  of our dataset";
8 run;
```

Here in this code, at first we load our dataset from library and stored it into the all_data variable then on the next section of code we used the total_value column for analysis. Therefore, we used a syntax called "univariate". This default syntax calculate the comprehensive analysis for our data. The output of the above code is given below:

comprehensive analysis using total value of our dataset

The UNIVARIATE Procedure
Variable: total_value

Moments			
N	646	Sum Weights	646
Mean	0.11959606	Sum Observations	77.2590543
Std Deviation	0.6960929	Variance	0.48454532
Skewness	15.0101888	Kurtosis	253.831219
Uncorrected SS	321.771609	Corrected SS	312.531731
Coeff Variation	582.036648	Std Error Mean	0.02738741

Basic Statistical Measures			
Location		Variability	
Mean	0.119596	Std Deviation	0.69609
Median	0.006160	Variance	0.48455
Mode	0.000000	Range	13.00000
		Interquartile Range	0.04433

Tests for Location: Mu0=0			
Test	Statistic	Pr > t	p Value
Student's t	t 4.366826	Pr > t	< .0001
Sign	M 323	Pr >= M	< .0001
Signed Rank	S 104490.5	Pr >= S	< .0001

Fig. 6. The UNIVARIATE Procedure Part 1

Quantiles (Definition 5)	
Level	Quantile
100% Max	1.30000E+01
99%	1.20784E+00
95%	7.03531E-01
90%	1.57543E-01
75% Q3	4.43416E-02
50% Median	6.15999E-03
25% Q1	1.49433E-05
10%	1.52957E-07
5%	8.59311E-08
1%	5.48593E-08
0% Min	4.90487E-08

Extreme Observations			
Lowest		Highest	
Value	Obs	Value	Obs
4.90487E-08	205	1.44841	342
5.34857E-08	521	1.70367	114
5.35449E-08	217	3.07790	646
5.35449E-08	204	10.33905	304
5.42481E-08	609	13.00000	152

Fig. 7. The UNIVARIATE Procedure Part 2

The above output (Figure 6,7) showed us that into our dataset we have mean value = 0.119596, median value =

0.006160, mode value = 0.000000, standard deviation = 0.69609, skewness value = 15.0101888 and finally the kurtosis value = 253.831219.

3) **Step 3:** The research is all about related to CO2 emission so here we used scatter plot with major sectors of a country with compare to population total. We got about 9 series of scatter plot of our dataset. The below code doing this overall scatter plot task for us. Firstly, we have to make our dataset separately with the help of series code filter. However, the researcher made the 9 dataset such as population, co2_emission, co2_emission_transport, co2_emission_electricity, co2_emission_manufacture, co2_emission_gaseous_fuel, co2_emission_liquid_fuel, co2_emission_solid_fuel, co2_emission_building and co2_other_sector data. After making all of this dataset we have to merge all the dataset so that we can get the total value for each series name. The name of the merged dataset is called 'compre_data'. Finally, our main dataset with the expected total value column is ready to do the main analysis work.

```

1 data total_population;
2   set co2_data.sheet1;
3   where series_code = 'SP.POP.TOTL';
4   population = total_value;
5 run;
6 data co2_emission_data;
7   set co2_data.sheet1;
8   where series_code = 'EN.ATM.CO2E.KT';
9   co2_emission = total_value;
10 run;
11 data co2_emission_transport;
12   set co2_data.sheet1;
13   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.TRAN.ZS';
14   co2_transpot = total_value;
15 run;
16 data co2_emission_electricity;
17   set co2_data.sheet1;
18   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.ETOT.ZS';
19   co2_electric = total_value;
20 run;
21 data co2_emission_manufacture;
22   set co2_data.sheet1;
23   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.MANF.ZS';
24   co2_manufacture = total_value;
25 run;
26 data co2_emission_gaseous_fuel;
27   set co2_data.sheet1;
28   where series_code = 'EN.ATM.CO2E.GF.ZS';
29   co2_gaseous = total_value;
30 run;
31 data co2_emission_liquid_fuel;
32   set co2_data.sheet1;
33   where series_code = 'EN.ATM.CO2E.LF.ZS';
34   co2_liquid = total_value;
35 run;
36 data co2_emission_solid_fuel;
37   set co2_data.sheet1;
38   where series_code = 'EN.ATM.CO2E.LF.ZS';
39   co2_solid = total_value;
40 run;
41 data co2_emission_building;
42   set co2_data.sheet1;
43   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.BLDG.ZS';
44   co2_building = total_value;
45 run;
46 data co2_other_sector;

```

```

47   set co2_data.sheet1;
48   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.OTHX.ZS';
49   co2_other = total_value;
50 run;
51 data compre_data;
52   merge total_population co2_emission_data
53   co2_emission_transport
54   co2_emission_electricity
55   co2_emission_manufacture
56   gdp_growth_data
57   co2_emission_gaseous_fuel
58   co2_emission_liquid_fuel
59   co2_emission_solid_fuel
60   co2_emission_building co2_other_sector;
61 run;
62 %let interval=co2_emission co2_transpot co2_electric
63   co2_manufacture co2_gaseous co2_liquid
64   co2_solid co2_building co2_other;
65 options nolabel;
66 proc sgscatter data=compre_data;
67   plot population*(&interval) / reg;
68   title "Associations of Interval Variables with
69   Population";
70 run;

```

On the last section of the code, the researcher used the variable interval where all the column is stored and then the 'sgscatter' function used. The 'compre_data' dataset value is used for making the scatter plot figure with compare all the interval with the population.

Fig. 8. Associations of Interval Variables with Population

Above (Figure 8) gave us a decision that the total population value comparing with other 9 series of our dataset. We found that co2_emission, co2_electric and co2_manufacture section has linear positive relation with the dataset. On the contrary, all of the other scatter pot showing small negative non-linear line for our dataset.

B. SAS (Correlation Analysis)

In this section, we are going to search our correlation of the dataset. The correlation analysis basically evaluate the strength of relationship between two numerically measured value, However this measured value can be called as continuous value.

1) **Step 1:** Here in this below code, we made different dataset which is needed for analysis from our main dataset. After that we select only the total value and finally we merge it to a new dataset. Importantly, In our dataset there are lot of series code there. Each series code mentioned different data of the dataset. As a result, we have to follow this procedure to separate our data and then analyze it.

```

1 /*-----correlation analysis
2 -----*/
3 data total_population;
4   set co2_data.sheet1;
5   where series_code = 'SP.POP.TOTL';
6   population = total_value;
7 run;
8 data co2_emission_data;
9   set co2_data.sheet1;
10  where series_code = 'EN.ATM.CO2E.KT';
11  co2_emission = total_value;
12 run;
13 data co2_emission_transport;
14   set co2_data.sheet1;
15   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.TRAN.ZS';
16   co2_transpot = total_value;
17 run;
18 data co2_emission_electricity;
19   set co2_data.sheet1;
20   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.ETOT.ZS';
21   co2_electric = total_value;
22 run;
23 data co2_emission_manufacture;
24   set co2_data.sheet1;
25   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.MANF.ZS';
26   co2_manufacture = total_value;
27 run;
28 data co2_emission_gaseous_fuel;
29   set co2_data.sheet1;
30   where series_code = 'EN.ATM.CO2E.GF.ZS';
31   co2_gaseous = total_value;
32 run;
33 data co2_emission_liquid_fuel;
34   set co2_data.sheet1;
35   where series_code = 'EN.ATM.CO2E.LF.ZS';
36   co2_liquid = total_value;
37 run;
38 data co2_emission_solid_fuel;
39   set co2_data.sheet1;
40   where series_code = 'EN.ATM.CO2E.SF.ZS';
41   co2_solid = total_value;
42 run;
43 data co2_emission_building;
44   set co2_data.sheet1;
45   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.BLDG.ZS';
46   co2_building = total_value;
47 run;
48 data co2_other_sector;
49   set co2_data.sheet1;
50   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.OTHX.ZS';
51   co2_other = total_value;
52 run;
53 data corr_table;
54   merge total_population co2_emission_data
55         co2_emission_transport
56         co2_emission_electricity
57         co2_emission_manufacture
58         gdp_growth_data
59         co2_emission_gaseous_fuel
60         co2_emission_liquid_fuel
61         co2_emission_solid_fuel

```

```

59   co2_emission_building co2_other_sector;
60 run;
61 %let interval=co2_emission co2_transpot co2_electric
62   co2_manufacture co2_gaseous co2_liquid
63   co2_solid co2_building co2_other;
64 ods graphics / reset=all imagemap;
65 proc corr data=corr_table rank
66 plots (only)=scatter (nvar=all ellipse=none);
67 var &interval;
68 with population;
69 title "Correlations and Scatter Plots With
70 Population,
71 CO2 Emission,CO2 transport, CO2 electricity,
72 CO2 manufacture, CO2 gaseous, CO2 liquid, CO2
73 solid,
74 CO2 building, CO2 other";
75 run;
76 title;

```

2) **Step 2:** The researcher followed the CORR procedure for finding out the correlation between the continuous values. However, all of the continuous value measured with the CO₂ emission series of our dataset. In the experimental dataset we have 34 countries there. As a result, every series will give us 34 values for each country. Below (Figure 9) all of the correlation and the scatter plots SAS Guide offered us.

Fig. 9. The CORR Procedure

3) **Step 3:** Scatter plot we got from the correlation analysis, one of them is showed here in this report (Figure 10).

Fig. 10. Scatter plot population vs CO₂_manufacturer

C. SAS (Regression Analysis)

Regression analysis is one of the most important method of statistical analysis. However, by using regression method we can find out he most reliable data from our dataset. Using this method, we can also identify the most important factors of data as well as we can identify which data we can ignore for our analysis.

In this part, the research going to work with the regression analysis with 9 models. Each model will describe connectivity of two type of variable. However, for this regression analysis, we selected our independent variable as a population and we changed the dependent variable for each model. The model with dependent and independent variable points are given below:

- CO₂ emission with population
- CO₂ emission from transport with population
- CO₂ emission from electricity with population
- CO₂ emission from manufacture with population
- CO₂ emission from gaseous fuel with population
- CO₂ emission from liquid fuel with population
- CO₂ emission from solid fuel with population
- CO₂ emission from building with population
- CO₂ emission from others with population

The dataset we already stored into our SAS environment. The process of storing the dataset into SAS environment as library are already described on the part A. However, for this regression analysis we need to make separate dataset so that we can do the regression analysis with the separate series of our dataset along with population.

```

1 /*-----regression analysis
2 -----*/
3 data total_population;
4   set co2_data.sheet1;
5   where series_code = 'SP.POP.TOTL';
6   population = total_value;
7 run;
8 data co2_emission_data;
9   set co2_data.sheet1;
10  where series_code = 'EN.ATM.CO2E.KT';
11  co2_emission = total_value;
12 run;
13 data co2_emission_transport;
14   set co2_data.sheet1;
15   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.TRAN.ZS';
16   co2_transpot = total_value;
17 run;
18 data co2_emission_electricity;
19   set co2_data.sheet1;
20   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.ETOT.ZS';
21   co2_electric = total_value;
22 run;
23 data co2_emission_manufacture;
24   set co2_data.sheet1;
25   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.MANF.ZS';
26   co2_manufacture = total_value;
27 run;
28 data co2_emission_gaseous_fuel;
29   set co2_data.sheet1;
30   where series_code = 'EN.ATM.CO2E.GF.ZS';
31   co2_gaseous = total_value;
32 run;
33 data co2_emission_liquid_fuel;
34   set co2_data.sheet1;

```

```

34   where series_code = 'EN.ATM.CO2E.LF.ZS';
35   co2_liquid = total_value;
36 run;
37 data co2_emission_solid_fuel;
38   set co2_data.sheet1;
39   where series_code = 'EN.ATM.CO2E.SF.ZS';
40   co2_solid = total_value;
41 run;
42 data co2_emission_building;
43   set co2_data.sheet1;
44   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.BLDG.ZS';
45   co2_building = total_value;
46 run;
47 data co2_other_sector;
48   set co2_data.sheet1;
49   where series_code = 'EN.CO2.OTHX.ZS';
50   co2_other = total_value;
51 run;
52 data regre_table;
53   merge total_population co2_emission_data
54   co2_emission_transport
55   co2_emission_electricity
56   co2_emission_manufacture
57   gdp_growth_data
58   co2_emission_gaseous_fuel
59   co2_emission_liquid_fuel
60   co2_emission_solid_fuel
61   co2_emission_building co2_other_sector;
62 run;
63 ods graphics;
64 proc reg data=regre_table;
65   model co2_emission=population;
66   model co2_transpot=population;
67   model co2_electric=population;
68   model co2_manufacture=population;
69   model co2_gaseous=population;
70   model co2_liquid=population;
71   model co2_solid=population;
72   model co2_building=population;
73   model co2_other=population;
74   title "Simple Regression with population as
75   Regressor";
76 run;
77 quit;

```

If we justify above code, we will see that we made the separate dataset by using series code filter. Each dataset holding their respected values with matching the series name.

1) **Model 1:** Lets start with the model1 where we did the regression between CO₂ emission and population value. Into the dataset. We have 34 countries and 19 series or categories to do our analysis.

Simple Regression with population as Regressor

The REG Procedure
Model: MODEL1
Dependent Variable: co2_emission

Number of Observations Read		34			
Number of Observations Used		34			
Analysis of Variance					
Source	DF	Squares	Mean Square	F Value	Pr > F
Model	1	0.24348	0.24348	5.04	0.0319
Error	32	1.58487	0.04953		
Corrected Total	33	1.83436			
Root MSE		0.22255	R-Square	0.1360	
Dependent Mean		0.08526	Adj R-Sq	0.1090	
Coeff Var		261.01206			
Parameter Estimates					
Variable	DF	Estimate	Standard Error	t Value	Pr > t
Intercept	1	0.04804	0.04161	1.15	0.2569
population	1	0.03154	0.01405	2.24	0.0319

Fig. 11. The REG Procedure MODEL 1

Above (Figure 11) gave us the data that we have 34 observation that means there is no missing values detected from our dataset for either CO2 emission and population column. For this two data column regression model created the F value = 5.04 and the p-value = 0.0319. The degrees of freedom or the Mean Square value we get from the table is 0.24948 and the Error which is unexplained by the model is 1.58487 The value of Root MSE = 0.22255 which is estimating the standard deviation of dependent variable at each value of the independent variable.

Fig. 12. Fit Diagnostics for MODEL 1

Fig. 13. Residuals for MODEL 1

Fig. 14. Fit Plot for MODEL 1

2) **Model 2:** From model2, we did the regression between CO2 emission from transport and population value. Into the dataset. We have followed the same procedure of Model1 to find out the output.

Fig. 15. The REG Procedure MODEL 2

For model2, we have same parameter into the output. For this transport and population data column regression model created the F value = 0.69 and the p-value = 0.4129. The degrees of freedom or the Mean Square value we get from the table is 0.03919 and the Error which is unexplained by the model is 1.82211 The value of Root MSE = 0.23862 which is estimating the standard deviation of dependent variable at each value of the independent variable.

Fig. 16. Fit Diagnostics for MODEL 2

Fig. 17. Residuals for MODEL 2

Fig. 18. Fit Plot for MODEL 2

3) **Model 3:** From model3, we get the regression output between CO₂ emission from electricity and population value.

Fig. 19. The REG Procedure MODEL 3

For model3, we have same parameter into the output. For this electricity and population data column regression model created the F value = 0.45 and the p-value = 0.5082. The degree of freedom or the Mean Square value we get from the table is 0.00097743 and the Error which is unexplained by the model is 0.06987. This error value is less than model1 and model2 both. The value of Root MSE = 0.04673 which is estimating the standard deviation of dependent variable at each value of the independent variable.

Fig. 20. Fit Diagnostics for MODEL 3

Fig. 21. Residuals for MODEL 3

Fig. 22. Fit Plot for MODEL 3

4) **Model 4:** From model4, we get the regression output between CO₂ emission from manufacture and population value.

Fig. 23. The REG Procedure MODEL 4

For model4, we have same parameter into the output. For this manufacture and population data column regression model created the F value = 0.75 and the p-value = 0.3944. The degree of freedom or the Mean Square value we get from the table is 0.00487 and the Error which is unexplained by the model is 0.20906. The value of Root MSE = 0.08083 which is estimating the standard deviation of dependent variable at each value of the independent variable.

Fig. 24. Fit Diagnostics for MODEL 4

Fig. 25. Residuals for MODEL 4

Fig. 26. Fit Plot for MODEL 4

5) **Model 5:** From model5, we get the regression output between CO₂ emission from gaseous fule and population value.

Simple Regression with population as Regressor

The REG Procedure
Model: MODEL5
Dependent Variable: co2_gasouse

Number of Observations Read 34
Number of Observations Used 34

Analysis of Variance					
Source	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F Value	Pr > F
Model	1	0.01725	0.01725	0.19	0.6664
Error	32	2.91718	0.09116		
Corrected Total	33	2.93444			

Root MSE	0.30193	R-Square	0.0059
Dependent Mean	0.10564	Adj R-Sq	-0.0252
Coeff Var	285.80068		

Parameter Estimates					
Variable	DF	Parameter Estimate	Standard Error	t Value	Pr > t
Intercept	1	0.11543	0.05646	2.04	0.0492
population	1	-0.00829	0.01906	-0.44	0.6664

Page Break

Simple Regression with population as Regressor

The REG Procedure
Model: MODEL5
Dependent Variable: co2_gasouse

Fig. 27. The REG Procedure MODEL 5

For model5, we have same parameter into the output. For this gaseous fuel and population data column regression model created the F value = 0.19 and the p-value = 0.6664. The degress of freedom or the Mean Square value we get from the table is 0.01725 and the Error which is unexplained by the model is 2.91718. The value of Root MSE = 0.30193 which is estimating the standard deviation of dependent variable at each value of the independent variable.

Fig. 28. Fit Diagnostics for MODEL 5

Fig. 29. Residuals for MODEL 5

Fig. 30. Fit Plot for MODEL 5

6) **Model 6:** From model6, we get the regression output between CO₂ emission from liquid fuel and population value.

For model6, we have same parameter into the output. For this liquid fuel and population data column regression model created the F value = 0.19 and the p-value = 0.6660. The degress of freedom or the Mean Square value we get from the table is 0.00032211 and the Error which is unexplained by the

Fig. 31. The REG Procedure MODEL 6

model is 0.05430. The value of Root MSE = 0.04119 which is estimating the standard deviation of dependent variable at each value of the independent variable.

Fig. 32. Fit Diagnostics for MODEL 6

Fig. 33. Residuals for MODEL 6

Fig. 34. Fit Plot for MODEL 6

7) **Model 7:** From model7, we get the regression output between CO2 emission from solid fuel and population value.

Fig. 35. The REG Procedure MODEL 7

For model7, we have same parameter into the output. For this solid fuel and population data column regression model created the F value = 0.27 and the p-value = 0.6058. The degrees of freedom or the Mean Square value we get from the table is 0.00055625 and the Error which is unexplained by the model is 0.06553. The value of Root MSE = 0.04525 which is estimating the standard deviation of dependent variable at each value of the independent variable.

Fig. 36. Fit Diagnostics for MODEL 7

Fig. 37. Residuals for MODEL 7

Fig. 38. Fit Plot for MODEL 7

Fig. 41. Residuals for MODEL 8

8) **Model 8:** From model8, we get the regression output between CO2 emission from building and population value.

Fig. 39. The REG Procedure MODEL 8

For model8, we have same parameter into the output. For this building and population data column regression model created the F value = 0.02 and the p-value = 0.8976. The degree of freedom or the Mean Square value we get from the table is 0.00135 and the Error which is unexplained by the model is 0.08035. The value of Root MSE = 0.28346 which is estimating the standard deviation of dependent variable at each value of the independent variable.

Fig. 42. Fit Plot for MODEL 8

9) **Model 9:** From model9, we get the regression output between CO₂ emission from others and population value.

Fig. 43. The REG Procedure MODEL 9

For model9, we have same parameter into the output. For this building and population data column regression model created the F value = 0.36 and the p-value = 0.5508. The degree of freedom or the Mean Square value we get from the table is 0.01142 and the Error which is unexplained by the model is 1.00571. The value of Root MSE = 0.17728 which is estimating the standard deviation of dependent variable at each value of the independent variable.

Fig. 40. Fit Diagnostics for MODEL 8

Fig. 44. Fit Diagnostics for MODEL 9

Fig. 45. Residuals for MODEL 9

Fig. 46. Fit Plot for MODEL 9

D. SAS (Comparative Analysis or Hypothesis Testing)

Comparative analysis is one kind process which basically do the comparison between items or data. However, It also find out the similarities and differences between the data. In this section, the researcher worked with the ANOVA testing to do the comparative analysis with the dataset. ANOVA is called as analysis of variance where it used the technique to compare the mean value of two or more groups of observations. For doing the comparative analysis or ANOVA, we need to select two types of variable. Firstly, continuous variable or dependent variable. Secondly, the independent variable or called a predictor.

Here for this dataset we used the ‘country_name’ for our independent variable or predictor. the total value is our dependent or continuous variable.

```

1 data all_data;
2   set co2_data.sheet1;
3 run;
4 ods graphics;
5 proc glm data=all_data plots=diagnostics;
6   class country_name;

```

```

7   model total_value=country_name;
8   means country_name / hovtest=levvene;
9   format country_name $country_name.;
10  title "One-Way ANOVA with Country Name as
11     Predictor";
12 run;
quit;

```

From the above code we can see that we have one dataset ‘all_data’ which is loading all the data form the SAS library/ the dataset is ready now to do the ANOVA test. We will get the expected column that we needed for our future analysis from our dataset. Here we used the GLM procedure to do the one way ANOVA test. We selected the country_name variable as our predictor value and the total_value column as our continuous value.

One-Way ANOVA with Country Name as Predictor	
The GLM Procedure	
Class Level Information	
Class	Levels Values
country_name	Algeria Armenia Austria Bangladesh Bhutan Brunei Canada China Costa Rica Czech Republic Denmark Ecuador France Germany Greece India Iraq Japan Malaysia Mexico Netherlands New Zealand Norway Pakistan Sri Lanka Saudi Arabia Sri Lanka Sweden Switzerland Turkey United Arab Emirates United Kingdom United States
	Number of Observations Read: 34
	Number of Observations Used: 34

Fig. 47. The GLM Procedure

One-Way ANOVA with Country Name as Predictor					
The GLM Procedure					
Dependent Variable: total_value					
Source	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F Value	Pr > F
Model	33	14.5807352	0.44184046	0.91	0.6186
Error	612	297.950954	0.4868480		
Corrected Total	645	312.5317307			
R-Square		Coeff Var	Root MSE	total_value Mean	
0.046554		583.4180	0.697745	0.119596	
Source	DF	Type I SS	Mean Square	F Value	Pr > F
country_name	33	14.58073523	0.44184046	0.91	0.6186
Source	DF	Type III SS	Mean Square	F Value	Pr > F
country_name	33	14.58073523	0.44184046	0.91	0.6186

Fig. 48. One-Way ANOVA Test

The output from our GLM procedure we mentioned our class name as country_name variable so its showed that we have 34 countries into our dataset. The second section of our output showing our F statistic and corresponding P value. The F statistic and corresponding P-value are reported in the analysis of variance table. The reported P value (0.6186) is greater than 0.05 That means we do not reject the null hypothesis and there is difference between the means.

Fig. 49. Fit Diagnostics for total_value

Secondly, the dataset we selected from the world bank website is not organized. Therefore, the dataset from the world bank website all of the series name value is separated for different countries. As a result, for any kind of analysis work we need to filter the dataset for specific series name and then we have to make another small dataset for that specific series name.

Thirdly, On the ANOVA testing, we found another problem. If we select only one series name for every country on the dataset, we found that the ANOVA testing result did not give us any P value and F value. As a result we have to do the ANOVA testing for all of the data. When the ANOVA try to grouping the values for only one series for all country, that time each country make only one group with a one series value. This is the main reason why the researcher select all the data from the dataset for the ANOVA testing so that it can create the F value and the P value.

Fourthly, In to the ANOVA testing output, we found a figure called distribution of total_value. In this figure, we saw there are a lot of country plotted. But we didn't find some country which is mentioned into our dataset. On the other hand, the plotting value from the diagram was overlapping each other.

Lastly, All of the analysis we used above correlation, regression and ANOVA, there we found all of the plot figure was little bit empty because we used only 19 category or the series value for the dataset. If we used the more data for our analysis, it will give us a clear vision of data plot figure.

Finally, After doing all of the analysis work, the researcher found some main point which should be followed for great visualization and analysis output. The point are given below:

- Dataset should be clean and normalized.
- More data value will create more understandable plotting.
- For ANOVA testing we can not use only one category. We should select multiple category so that it can create the grouping.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this research helped us to find out our decision about the carbon dioxide emission. This research depends on different countries and its various sectors of carbon dioxide production. However, we saw that population of a country effects a lot on carbon dioxide emission. There are other sectors we discovered with the dataset and we found that Carbon dioxide emission on transport, manufacture and electricity sectors producing most of the carbon gas for that country. On the other hand, there are negative relation we found with the fuel sectors of a country with the carbon dioxide emission. This research also discovered statistical analysis which helped to get clear idea about the carbon prediction. the main finding of this research is to find out the effects on various sector of a country how they contributing carbon to the world and also which sectors mostly affecting the world. If we consider those sector and take the necessary step to all those sectors to reduce the carbon, it will be a great help for our world near future. Finally, after doing all of this analytical work the research gave us the exact parameter to deal with the

carbon and also the objectives what the human being should consider to reduce carbon dioxide from the environment.

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